

SPECIAL ISSUE: The Wicked Problems in the Governance of the Just Green Transitions: between Territorial Resilience and Foresight.

Mapping Digital Spatiality: The Online Debate over Italy's National Radioactive Waste Repository

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Abstract

This study examines how the controversy over Italy's proposed National Radioactive Waste Repository unfolds in hybrid digital environments, and what this implies for territorial planning and governance. Radioactive waste poses distinctive temporal and spatial challenges, and siting disputes exemplify wicked problems in which ecological sustainability, spatial planning, economic change, and social equity intersect and require continuous negotiation.

Building on Issue Spatiality, the article analyses how online actors construct spatial imaginaries by mobilising proximity, scale, territorial identity to legitimise or contest competing narratives. The methodology adopts a digital methods approach integrating Social Network Analysis, Natural Language Processing and qualitative content analysis.

Findings show a territorially segmented digital public sphere dominated by activists, local media, and regional voices, with limited cross-regional bridging. Within these segmented arenas, visibility is largely captured by oppositional mobilisation, while institutional framings are less prominent and frequently challenged through legitimacy and procedural-justice claims. The study identified regionally scaled resistance dynamics consistent with NIMYR ("Not In My Region") positions, linking territorial belonging to multi-level governance tensions.

By relating digitally produced geographies of contestation to the institutional spatial rationality embedded in the CNAPI map, the article highlights the need for scale-sensitive and more coordinated communication strategies.

Keywords

Digital Public sphere; Issue spatiality; Digital Methods; Just Green Transitions; Radioactive Waste.

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Introduction

“Our planet is full”. With this sentence the sociologist and philosopher Zygmunt Bauman in his book *Wasted Lives* (2004) highlights the acute crisis of human waste disposal, referring to the disappearance of “no man’s land” that, throughout modern history, served as dumping grounds for humanity’s by-products.

Among these, radioactive waste stands out for its unique temporal dimension: a material whose toxicity unfolds over millennia, demanding a rethinking of temporality, responsibility, and justice (Wyck, 2004).

Nuclear technologies have profoundly shaped modernity: they have powered nations, influenced the geopolitical order and promised abundant energy for a sustainable future (Melchionda, 2023). The longevity of radioactive waste leaves an indelible trace on the landscapes of our time, prompting scholars to describe this epoch as the Nuclear Anthropocene (Wyck, 2004).

Radioactive waste governance embodies the wickedness of the Just Green Transitions (JGT): a process in which ecological sustainability, spatial planning and territorial governance, economic transformation, and socio-spatial justice intersect in ways that generate complexity and conflict (Rittel & Webber, 1973; Brunnengräber, 2019; Lagerlöf, 2023; Shaker & Persico, 2024). The interests of diverse stakeholders create governance conflicts (Jessop, 2011), amplifying uncertainty and mistrust.

This paper examines the controversy surrounding Italy’s National Radioactive Waste Repository as a paradigmatic case through which to explore the online debate and its spatial declinations.

The National Radioactive Waste Repository in Italy

On 4 January 2021, a breaking news in Italy concerning the management of radioactive waste sparked widespread public debate: Sogin (the public company that manages nuclear waste in Italy) published documentation and the project for a National Radioactive Waste Repository (from now on National Repository). Among the documents, what caught people’s attention the most was the National Map of Most Suitable Areas (*Carta Nazionale Aree più Idonee –CNAPI*), which shows the areas with potential suitability to host the National Repository. Thirteen Provinces are involved, comprising 67 different locations classified as “Solid candidates” (12 areas), “high interest” (11 areas) and “less interesting” (44 areas).

Figure 1. The CNAPI map showing the 67 candidate areas distributed across Piedmont (8 areas), Tuscany-Lazio (24 areas), Basilicata-Puglia (17 areas), Sardinia (14 areas) and Sicily (4 areas). (Source: www.depositonazionale.it)

The National Repository is a surface environmental infrastructure that will allow for the permanent safe storage of radioactive waste (currently stored within dozens of temporary repositories across the country). The facility will allow for the disposal of low-level, medium and high level radioactive waste produced by the operation and decommissioning of nuclear facilities but also from the daily activities of nuclear medicine, industry and research which will continue to be produced in Italy (Deposito Nazionale, n.d.). The publication of the map mobilised public opinion across Italy, igniting a debate that drew in national and local politicians, ecological organisations (such as Legambiente, WWF, Greenpeace) and grassroots movements. What began as a technical planning exercise rapidly evolved into a socially and politically charged controversy, intertwining environmental, territorial, and economic concerns.

This article examines how the debate over radioactive waste developed among Italian social media users, situating it at the crossroads of environmental sustainability, socio-spatial justice, and economic policy. It builds on the premise that digital and physical spaces are deeply interconnected rather than separate spheres (Jurgenson, 2012), with online communication that

reproduces and amplifies local identities, relationships, and conflicts from the offline world (Neely & Collins, 2018; Hagen et al., 2018). Thus, the digital sphere functions not as an abstract realm but as an extension of territorial life, where communities negotiate belonging, legitimacy, and authority.

At this intersection, the governance of radioactive waste becomes a site of negotiation between top-down planning and bottom-up agency, between institutional control and local autonomy. The Italian case exemplifies how certain aspects of the JGT are complex and difficult to resolve, characterised by uncertainty and controversy.

Theoretical Framework

Place-Based Contestation & Environmental Justice

Opposition to this type of infrastructure can be understood as a form of place-protective action that emerges when development is perceived to threaten place-related identity processes and to disrupt emotional attachment (Devine-Wright, 2009). The formation of self-identity occurs not only through mechanisms of differentiation between self and others, but also through relationships with objects and with the spaces and places in which these objects are situated (Proshansky et al., 2014). Place attachment has been conceptualised through three principal dimensions: the personal dimension, the psychological dimension, and the place-dimension (Scannell & Gifford, 2010). The personal dimension includes both an individual component (personal connection) and a group component (shared symbolic meanings attributed to a place). Psychological processes, in turn, operate across three aspects: an affective aspect concerning emotional bonds; a cognitive aspect encompassing memories and knowledge; and a behavioural aspect grounded in the desire to remain close to a place. The place dimension is articulated at two levels: a social level (attachment to places that facilitate social relations) and a physical level (attachment to places that provide resources supportive of one's goals). This place dimension can be examined across multiple spatial scales (home, neighbourhood, city, province, region, etc.).

Taken together, these dynamics help delineate the foundations of activism examined in this study, which is often loosely subsumed under the label NIMBY¹ ("Not In My Back Yard"). Italy has a long-standing and institutionalised NIMBY culture: since 2004, an observatory coordinated by a non-profit organisation with support from the Presidency of the Council of Ministers has monitored controversial projects. Its data show that energy facilities (62.5%), waste treatment

¹ NIMBY denotes protest by members of a local community against the construction of public works with significant impacts (such as major transport corridors, quarries, residential or industrial developments, waste-to-energy facilities, landfills, hazardous-substance storage sites, power plants, and similar infrastructure) in an area perceived as proximate to everyday interests, while the same works may be tolerated if located elsewhere (De Luca, 2012).

plants (25.9%), and infrastructure (8.7%) dominate contested works, with key reasons for opposition being environmental impacts (39%), health risks (13.6%), and quality-of-life concerns (11.7%) (Buffoli et al., 2016).

As several scholars have noted, however, NIMBY is a label that should be employed with caution (Burningham, 2000), since it is necessary to distinguish between opportunism and the legitimacy of the claims advanced (Feldman & Turner, 2014). The phenomenon is particularly prominent in relation to renewable-energy facilities, and empirical work has shown that proximity plays a decisive role in shaping public attitudes towards specific projects (van der Horst, 2007). A consequential question, then, is whether digital space also intervenes in these logics of proximity and how it may shape citizens' environmental justice claims.

This case study is especially suitable because, as Walker (2012) notes, the geographical patterning of radioactive-waste storage sites constituted one of the earliest focal points of statistical research on environmental justice. Local resistance is typically intertwined with decision-making processes, and distrust in the safety guarantees offered by public authorities often translates into local political mobilisation. Over time, the concept of environmental justice has been reformulated and expanded along three directions: the definition of "environment;" the factors underpinning the production of "environmental injustice;" and divergent interpretations of "justice" itself. The debate has thereby widened to encompass additional arenas such as climate change and climate justice, as well as issues related to food and energy (Schlosberg, 2013). The case considered here falls within these expanded domains insofar as the National Repository aligns with the principles of the JGT, particularly with the notion of "justice" understood as a shared responsibility that each EU Member State must assume in managing its own radioactive waste (Council of the European Union, 2011).

Hybrid Spatiality & Issue Spatiality In Digitally Mediated Controversies

Across the discussion developed thus far, the spatial component is central. The aim of this contribution is to extend the analysis by incorporating the notion of hybrid spatiality, which foregrounds dynamics of communication and sociability within digital space. According to de Souza e Silva et al. (2024) hybrid space can be conceptualised as a spatial logic composed of three main components. The first is mobilities, referring both to people's physical movements through space and to the circulation of information across networks. The second is connectivities, which concerns social and informational networks. The third is sociabilities, referring to communication among connected individuals. It follows that hybrid space is characterised by situations in which mobility is not equitably distributed, connections are diverse and sociability cannot be taken for granted, highlighting other fundamental components

such as agency (personal choice), awareness (transparency and knowledge) and access (to mobility and technology) (de Souza e Silva et al., 2024). With the rise of digital technologies, the barriers to entering public discourse have dramatically declined, leading to the proliferation of issue publics: actors who unite around shared concerns and issues (Bennett et al., 2015). Within digital platforms, this shift has expanded participation and diversified the range of voices (Waldherr et al., 2021), but it has also multiplied the complexity and volatility of public debates, particularly when social media is part of the equation (Wetts et al., 2024).

To unpack how these dynamics operate within digital communication, this study adopts Stoltenberg's (2021) framework of Issue Spatiality, a theoretical and methodological lens that connects the spatial and communicative dimensions, and that allows to trace how territorial resilience is enacted through digital discourse. Issue Spatiality builds on Martina Löw's (2008) sociology of space, which conceptualises a duality of space: space has the power to shape social events but is also continuously produced by social practices. Stoltenberg (2021) extends Löw's framework to address the spatial dynamics of issues in contemporary digitally mediated public spheres. This framework offers a conceptual and methodological bridge between the socio-spatial complexity of wicked problems and the communicative practices enacted in digital environments of hybrid spaces.

A key point is that in digital environments, resident and non-resident communication co-exist (Stoltenberg, 2021). Resident communication involves actors physically or symbolically embedded in a specific territory who use digital media to organise, mobilise, and gain visibility (Jackson & Foucault Welles, 2015). Non-resident communication comes from actors external to the place (journalists, institutions, citizens elsewhere) who participate in the debate through mediated representations.

Between these poles, there are hybrid forms, where residents share mass-media coverage of their territories, or non-residents adopt local frames of reference. This interplay produces hybrid spatialities in which the local and the global intertwine, what Roudometof (2023) terms the "glocal" condition.

Issue spatiality should be understood as the combination of three interrelated dimensions (Pfetsch et al., 2019): the spatiality of actors, which refers to their location, positionality, and relational proximity within the digital communicative space; the spatiality of networks, which captures how digital actors interconnect, forming infrastructures that mediate issue circulation; and the spatiality of content, which concerns how topics and issues embodied in texts, images, and discourses encode places and territories, constructing symbolic geographies of meaning.

By analysing these dimensions, Issue Spatiality illuminates how communication produces not only representations of space but also spatial relations themselves: how digital discourse

creates territorial imaginaries that shape perception, legitimacy, and policy. Within these networked public spheres, discourse evolves into multiple sub-issues and opposing viewpoints, often animated by personal narratives that grow into activist frameworks (Bennett & Segerberg, 2012). If communication that produces spatial relations is characterised by defects or anomalies, the discourse that follows tends to project these shortcomings onto perceptions, legitimacy, and ultimately policy outcomes.

Information Dynamics & Territorial Segmentation.

The digital sphere, unfortunately, is particularly affected by what scholars have termed the information problem (Born & Edgington, 2017; Fallis, 2015; Stahl, 2006). Researchers commonly distinguish among misinformation, to indicate unintentional inaccuracies, often circulated by trusted peers (Fetzer, 2004; Shu et al., 2020), disinformation to underline the intentional dissemination of false or manipulative content (Shu et al., 2020), and online propaganda, consisting of content that may be factually accurate yet strategically framed to advance partisan or ideological agendas (Tucker et al., 2018). Propaganda differs from misinformation by its strategic use of framing aimed to discredit opponents (Born & Edgington, 2017; Sanovich et al., 2018). Hyper-partisan media are characterised by news content that (even if not entirely fabricated) covers events with a strong partisan bias (Pennycook & Rand, 2021) and are often accused of being important incubators and vectors of disinformation (Faris et al., 2017). They employ sensationalist tones to appeal to audiences' emotions (Mourão & Robertson, 2019), and their perceived quality depends largely on ideological alignment with their audience (Metzger et al., 2020). Recent studies have shown that moral framing is particularly salient in hyper-partisan content, especially the care moral frame, which emphasises protecting individuals from harm and injustice (Xu et al., 2020).

The presence of an information problem in online network ecosystems can contribute to the structuring of issue publics into more weakly connected components (Bright, 2018). In this case study, this aspect does not occur as generic "fragmentation" but rather as territorial segmentation, namely regionally anchored communicative communities. Within these segmented publics, oppositional narratives tend to become dominant, fostering oppositional mobilisation and territorially coded legitimacy disputes. Crucially, misinformation and hyper-partisan framing do not only circulate claims; they also perform spatial work by attributing responsibility to particular governance levels and territories (e.g., local administrations versus the state) and by hardening insider–outsider distinctions (e.g., "our territory" versus external imposition), thereby linking legitimacy disputes to territorially rooted imaginaries (Matthes, 2009; Muis et al., 2019). Rather than resolving uncertainty, these dynamics can undermine trust and

stabilise contestation-reproducing characteristics commonly associated with wicked controversies, where expertise, responsibility, and acceptable risk remain persistently disputed. In the case of the Italian National Radioactive Waste Repository, this mechanism becomes particularly evident: digital networks mediate the way in which territorial conflicts are framed, remembered and amplified, influencing both local perceptions and debates on national governance (Tucker et al., 2018).

Against this background, the article investigates how the controversy surrounding the Repository has been constructed and negotiated across Italy's digital public sphere. The study focuses on how digital discourse contributes to the formation of spatial imaginaries of risk, resistance, and adaptation, revealing how environmental governance issues are entangled with communication dynamics that generate both territorial segmentation and resilience.

Accordingly, the research addresses the following questions:

- 1) How do different actors contribute to the networked spatialisation of the National Radioactive Waste Repository issue, and how do their communicative practices (including disinformation or hyper-partisan framing) shape the visibility and legitimacy of competing narratives?
- 2) Which spaces and places (physical, symbolic, and digital) emerge as focal points in the public debate on radioactive waste, and how do they reflect the relational production of territorial identities and conflicts?

To answer these questions, the paper employs a multi-method digital approach combining network mapping, visual analysis, and qualitative content analysis. This reveals a heterogeneous media ecosystem in which national and local actors interact, producing both cross-regional connections and region-specific clusters, identified as NIMYR (Not In MY Region) communities. The spatialisation of the issue exposes a debate that simultaneously transcends national borders, by recalling distant episodes such as Chernobyl and Fukushima, and expands temporally, by reactivating memories of Scanzano Jonico (Zinn, 2017).

Visual and textual analyses together capture the texture of this debate: a highly emotional environment where propaganda and disinformation can flourish. Through digital interactions, communities reinterpret environmental conflicts and reorganise their sense of space and belonging under conditions of uncertainty. Such complexity underscores the political implications of unregulated digital communication ecosystems and the need for transparent and well-structured communication strategies to prevent decision-making paralysis and oppositional mobilisation.

Methodology

Investigating technology-mediated phenomena requires adapting social-scientific approaches to contexts marked by fast-paced technological change and shifting platforms. These challenges are represented by the nature of the site of inquiry, the digital medium, crossing geographic boundaries and spatial divisions, social structures of hierarchy and power, national and political boundaries, and educational divisions, which are most evident in physical spaces (Kaur-Gill & Dutta, 2017). The research relies on Digital Methods (Marres, 2015; Rogers, 2019) to collect and process data from the social media platforms Twitter (now X) and Facebook. This paper adopts the use of the previous name Twitter because it refers to the platform prior to the acquisition and rebranding, coherently with the data collection period. Digital methods refer to research approaches that work with data generated within online platforms to study collective patterns, social transformation, and cultural practices. This contribution methodologically merges Digital Methods with Issue Spatiality (Stoltenberg, 2024), which could be understood as a macro-level characteristic of public issue discourses (Waldherr, 2017, p. 544), manifesting at the output level of these discourses (Gerhards & Neidhardt, 1991, pp. 34–35). This is particularly evident in the use of place names in public communication, known as place-naming (Gutsche, 2014; Stoltenberg, 2021; Wiard & Pereira, 2019). Place-naming refers to the act of publicly referring to specific places in various contexts and represents an empirically observable social practice that fundamentally shapes and guides the concept of Issue Spatiality. Through repeated acts of place-naming by many different actors over time, spatial patterns become visible. The understanding of Issue Spatiality as a macro-level property highlights that no individual piece of public communication (be it a news article, statement by a politician, or tweet) creates an issue space. Instead, the repeated invocation of specific places in relation to issues by a heterogeneous set of actors gives room for a public issue.

Within issue discourses, place-naming works in conjunction with a variety of other message features, such as the discussion of particular sub-issues, use of communicative styles, or discursive connections to other places, to create specific contexts in which places are relevant (Stoltenberg, 2021). Social media data are analysed looking for geographic information in the form of place-naming (Gutsche, 2014; Wiard & Pereira, 2019), with the purpose to spatialise the phenomenon under study (Stoltenberg, 2021; McKittrick et al., 2023), by merging Natural Language Processing (NLP) to extract location information and Social Network Analysis (SNA) to map the extracted information. The research design also involves qualitative content analysis and image analysis aimed at gathering additional details to help contextualise the quantitative analysis and add some nuances to the debate.

Data Collection

Data collection comprises two sequential steps. The first consists of defining the query design that identifies the keywords and their combination to collect (through Twitter’s API or Meta’s dashboards) reliable and consistent data to analyse. For the purpose of the research two queries have been defined: one containing keywords referring to nuclear/atomic energy and radioactivity (Q1) and the second referring to waste and storage (Q2). The final query (Qf) is the intersection of the previous ones, which allows to strictly select the subtopic “waste storage” debated in the context of “nuclear and radioactivity.”

Figure 2. The figure sums-up the query design for the research where Qf is the intersection between the queries Q1= nuclear OR atomic* OR radioattiv*(radioactivity) and Q2= scori* OR rifiut*(waste) OR residu*(residue) OR scart* (by-product) OR deposit* (repository/storage) OR discarica (landfill). (Source: Author’s own elaboration).*

The second step consists of capturing data. Data has been collected from Twitter via 4CAT (Peeters & Hagen, 2022), using Twitter’s APIs for academic research, while data from Facebook has been accessed with CrowdTangle (2022). The first difference is that Twitter allows data collection from every user, while Meta only gives access to public content from verified accounts, public pages, and public groups. The final datasets contain 10,847 Facebook posts and 12,669 tweets. Both datasets were uploaded to 4CAT for the SNA and to CorText (Breucker et al., 2016) for the NLP phase that will be explained below.

The analysis focuses on the six-month period following the publication of the official documents, from January to June 2021, which was considered sufficient to capture the bulk of the social media debate that broke out in early January and reached peak intensity shortly thereafter. This temporal window allows to observe how the timing of communication (whether before, during, or after key policy events) shapes interpretive frames and public responses (Chong & Druckman, 2007). The temporality of information circulation is not a neutral factor: in digital environments, the speed and sequencing of messages affect visibility, reach, and emotional resonance, often privileging immediacy over accuracy (Bruns, 2018). These temporal

and spatial dynamics together determine how users and institutions construct meaning, align around issues, and position themselves in public discourse.

Natural Language Processing & Machine Learning

The NLP is used to extract both locations and peculiar terms of the debate from the posts' text body. The location identification relies on machine learning, with a Convolutional Neural Network from the SpaCy library that executes a Named Entity Recogniser (NER) task able to recognise countries, cities, states, and other spatial references. The algorithm works as a black box and has been trained with news and media for the Italian language.

The peculiar terms will be extracted with a Terms Extraction task that relies on NLTK (Natural Language ToolKit). The text body is pre-processed in three phases: Part-of-Speech tagging, chunking, and stemming. The Part-of-Speech tagging tool categorises terms based on their grammatical category, such as noun, adjective, verb, or adverb. During the chunking phase, tags are used to identify noun phrases in the corpus; a noun phrase is defined as a sequence of nouns and adjectives. This stage creates the set of possible multi-terms. The stemming phase is dedicated to managing multiple terms that can be grouped together if they share the same stem. For example, singular and plurals are automatically placed into the same class (for example, "municipality" and "municipalities" are two possible forms of the stem "municipalit-"). Snowball stemmers are used for French, German, and Italian (Bird et al., 2009). The most relevant terms are chosen based on a balance of specificity and frequency. By default, specificity is calculated as a χ^2 score (sum of all terms). It is also conceivable to utilise a simpler G^2 score (GF-IDF for Global Frequency/Inverse Document Frequency derived from the well-known Term Frequency/Inverse Document Frequency, TF-IDF).

Table 1. Example results of particular terms extraction. Attribute *n* describes the number of words in the main form, *C*-value describes the frequency score, and *chi2* describes the specificity score.

Stem	Main form (IT)	Main form (EN)	Forms (IT)	n	C-value	Specificity chi2
depos nazionale rif	Deposito Nazionale dei rifiuti	national waste repository	Deposito Nazionale dei rifiuti Deposito nazionale rifiuti Deposito Nazionale di rifiuti	4	170.77	4546.50
rif siti stoccaggio	siti di stoccaggio dei rifiuti	waste storage sites	siti di stoccaggio dei rifiuti Siti di stoccaggio di rifiuti	5	49.64	4890.95
costruzione depos	costruzione del deposito	construction of the repository	costruzione del deposito costruzione del Deposito costruzione di deposito	3	212.44	3857.34
dell'ente nazionale parco presidente	presidente dell'Ente Parco Nazionale	president of the National Park Authority	presidente dell'Ente Parco Nazionale	4	33.76	4047.30
funghi mini-centrali	fungaia di mini-centrali	mushrooming of mini power plants	fungaia di mini-centrali	3	61.37	8427.10
centrali ex-scorie	scorie delle ex-centrali	waste from former plants	scorie delle ex-centrali	4	35.74	1955.26
infranzione procedura	procedura di infranzione	infranzione procedure	procedura di infranzione	3	39.34	1987.91
discussioni forti	forte discussione	heated discussion	forte discussione	2	50.36	4451.22
di radioattive scorie	DI SCORIE RADIOATTIVE	of radioactive waste	DI SCORIE RADIOATTIVE	3	41.70	2657.11
depos nazionale scorie	Deposito nazionale scorie	national waste repository	Deposito nazionale scorie Deposito Nazionale scorie	3	79.43	2748.99

Both locations and peculiar terms will be indexed in the dataset, allowing to elaborate a bipartite graph that shows the relations between the most prominent terms that describe the issues and the locations extracted, which will allow for data spatialisation by using SNA as described in the following paragraph.

Social Network Analysis

The SNA will be performed using the dedicated software Gephi (Bastian et al., 2009) in order to map the actors' spatiality and the issue spatiality. Regarding the actors' spatiality and their network, this contribution will follow the principles of Actor-Network Theory (Latour, 2007), including in the actor definition both human agents (users, pages, groups) and non-human entities (newspapers, websites, or platforms). This choice is due to social networking sites including the feature of hyperlinking, with references to material on different social media

networks and online spaces constituting a common dynamic. The deliberate use of this resource (Ryfe et al., 2016) shapes networks (Fu & Shumate, 2017) and creates an integrated media landscape (Singer, 2019) that impacts how people discover, absorb, and disseminate news (Martin & Dwyer, 2019). Users inside this ecosystem can select the preferred option to meet their communicative goals, creating a customised social media ecology (Bayer et al., 2020).

To map the spatiality of actors and their network, the research assumes that actors (users, groups, pages, news sites, newspapers) containing a clear topological reference can be spatialised in those same geographic coordinates (Samuel & Sharma, 2021). In that way, considering both usernames and web domains, is possible to shape a network of information dissemination exploiting “people’s references to locations that represent momentary social hotspots” (Stefanidis et al., 2013) to derive the spatial characteristics of the entire network. The actor graph traces the relationships between different actors that appear in the same post/content, spatialising those that contain geographic names and applying a ForceAtlas algorithm to infer the locations of other actors and the network’s flow.

In order to map the most debated issues, an additional bipartite graph has been produced to trace the relationships between the places extracted with the NER algorithm and the peculiar terms extracted with NLTK. In the following step, the places are spatialised, fixing their location on the map, while the themes are spatialised using the selected ForceAtlas algorithm. Since the extracted places have different dimensional scales (from continent to small towns), the research design opted for a trade-off of accuracy at the regional level. This means that larger entities are spatialised outside the Italian map, while small cities will be spatialised in their home region, paying attention to map readability.

Applying the ordering algorithm called ForceAtlas to shape the connections is possible to highlight main clusters, communities, and relevant nodes. The ForceAtlas algorithm is a force-directed algorithm that has been chosen for its focus on quality, meaning “being useful to explore real data,” and good readability, to allow a rigorous interpretation of the graph with the fewest biases possible.

Qualitative content analysis

The qualitative analysis examined individual items/posts as the unit of analysis, including accompanying text, embedded images/videos, and hyperlinks where present. From the full corpus (23,516 items), a time-stratified sample (n = 420) has been extracted to ensure coverage of the main phases of the debate and to support interpretation of patterns not fully captured by quantitative summaries.

The iterative qualitative content analysis has been carried out in a manually coded spreadsheet, performing at first a descriptive coding cycle to capture key attributes of each item (actor type, stance, referenced places and scales, and the presence of content features related to information disorder). The codebook was developed inductively through repeated reading and refinement, while a subset of categories was specified deductively (notably the distinctions between misinformation/disinformation/propaganda and hyper-partisan framing). In the analysis, disinformation has been defined as items containing verifiably false or misleading claims that also display indicators of deception (e.g., fabricated attributions, manipulated images, or “share before it gets deleted” rhetoric). In order to avoid attributing intent at the individual level, disinformation has been defined through the verifiability of content and observable indicators of deception. Hyper-partisan framing is treated as a mechanism for defining boundaries and assigning responsibilities, through which territorial identities (“us here/our home/my region”) and responsibilities (“the Govern/the State/the EU”) are constructed and contested in the debate.

The classification of actor-type and stance coding was used in relation to RQ1 to identify which actors amplified particular narratives and how communicative practices including hyper-partisan framing and information-disorder features were associated with claims to credibility, visibility, and legitimacy. Regarding RQ2, the coded references to specific places (municipalities/provinces/regions) and the invoked scale (local/regional/national), allowed to reconstruct the spatial imaginaries through which the controversy was articulated and to identify how territorial identities and conflicts were produced relationally across physical, symbolic, and digital spaces.

In addition to item-level content coding, the study carried out a qualitative inspection of the visual layer of the debate by extracting 1,466 images from Twitter. The software ImageSorter allowed to organise the images by exploiting the circulation of clustered “metapictures” on the platform (Rogers, 2021). This analysis identified recurrent objects/events and recognisable social–geographic contexts and examined symbols and visual codes to interpret implicit messages and value references. Visual findings informed theme refinement for RQ1 (visibility/legitimacy of narratives) and RQ2 (places, territorial imaginaries, and symbolic geographies).

Ethical Guidelines

The research took into consideration the ethical dimension to more adequately address the issues of anonymisation, pseudonymisation, and data minimisation, following the policies of the University and the “public good principle.” In light of the above considerations, different

operations have been applied to the document, such as blurring images with clearly visible faces, avoiding citation of private profiles by presenting only aggregate data, clearly distinguishing public figures with in-text citations, and citing channels that do not contain private personal information.

Results

Actors & Network Spatiality

The map below (Figure 3) has the main intention of supplying an answer to the first research question concerning actors and network spatial dynamics. It maps the ecosystem by showing the relationships between the main actors: social media users but also groups, pages, and external platforms, websites, and news media, which by interacting online create an interconnected information flow. Node placement should be interpreted primarily as a networked digital spatialisation rather than as a literal representation of physical location. Red nodes with known, inferred geographic information (e.g., region-level coordinates derived from explicit location cues) are plotted in geographic space to indicate the territorial anchors of part of the debate. By contrast, white nodes for which no reliable location could be assigned are included to preserve the structure of the online interaction network, but they are not intended to represent geographically situated actors. These nodes are plotted only to visualise their relational proximity to geolocated actors (i.e., their digital connectedness within the network) and should therefore be read as occupying digital space rather than physical space.

Among the main actors, it is possible to spot “RNA – Rete Nazionale Antinucleare” (translated as Antinuclear National Network), a page with 40K followers which shows the convergence in the debate of actors involved in activism against nuclear energy for civil purposes.

Other major nodes are connected to Legambiente, an Italian environmental association that is heir to the early eco-groups and the anti-nuclear movement that developed in Italy from the mid-1970s. The actors are mainly located in the centre and tied to Lazio actors. The reason might be the countercultural leadership of Legambiente Lazio, which has been open to dialogue about the National Repository, compared with the position of the other regional divisions, which have strongly advocated against it (Alaimo, 2023).

Some actors are clearly linked to specific political parties. In Lazio, in particular, several social media pages center on the right-wing party Fratelli d’Italia, which emerges as one of the main actors in the regional debate. Another main node of the debate is YouTube, which is positioned on the southern part of the map, strongly connected to Puglia and Basilicata actors. YouTube is a key node that deserves further attention since its increasing dominance as a central actor of today’s online information ecosystem (Soriano & Gaw, 2022).

Issue Spatiality

The Figure below (Figure 4) has the main purpose of providing an answer to the second research question, showing the issue spatiality by mapping the places (extracted through NER) with the peculiar terms of the debate (extracted through NLTK). The analysis shows several thematic clusters that have mainly a regional dimension but also highlights how the spatiality of the debate crosses national borders. This analysis has been implemented using only Facebook data which, allowing for longer posts than Twitter, results in more structured text that performed better in the peculiar terms extraction task.

Figure 4. The Issue spatiality elaborated with Facebook data. The place-issue graph is elaborated with Gephi and overlaid on the Italy map. (Source: Author's own elaboration).

The main keywords are relative to the National Repository itself, with references to radioactive waste and nuclear waste. All the regions show clear messages against the National Repository, depicting highly radical positions on the subject. Each region presents some peculiarity: in Sicily, is possible to identify references to the Regional President Nello Musumeci, underlining the political nature of the debate. The peculiarity of the debate in Puglia and Basilicata is the presence of references to the episode of Scanzano Jonico (Bortoletti, 2004) and to the National Park (Alta Murgia), in whose proximity a number of potential sites have been identified, underlining particular attention to natural heritage sites. Moving the focus to the

central cluster is possible to identify other narratives related to two nuclear sites: the closed nuclear power plant in Latina (currently a temporary radioactive waste Repository) and the aborted project of the nuclear power plant in Montalto di Castro, at the border between the regions of Lazio and Tuscany. Peculiar keywords in this case are “securing,” “cubic metres of waste,” and “low activity” with respect to the Latina temporary waste repository.

Another thematic cluster revolves around the locations of Europe and Ispra. Europe is intended as a reference to the EU, while Ispra has a dual meaning: as a municipality in Varese province where the Joint Research Centre² (JRC) headquarters are located, and as the acronym for *Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale* (Higher Institute for Environmental Protection and Research). The content mainly refers to this second institute, which is the agency in charge of defining the criteria adopted to draft the CNAPI. The related keywords describe nuances of the informational process such as “exclusion criteria,” “structural check,” “large consultation,” “category association,” “waste from ex-nuclear plant,” “extreme transparency,” “UNESCO sites,” and “fake news diffusion.”

Finally, another thematic cluster orbits around the three locations that most prominently evoke (with an obvious negative declination) the collective imagination inherent in nuclear power: Hiroshima, Chernobyl, and Fukushima. Here the discourse, on the one hand, seems concerned given the prominence of the terms and the presence of secondary terms such as “transition to the other world” and “cancer deaths.” On the other hand, the discourse seems to be approached with irony, with terms such as “aerosol from the mini reactor,” “fabulous grilling,” and “cute little mushroom cloud.”

Qualitative insights

The Figure below (Figure 5) is a graphic elaboration in which the images are sorted by colour similarity. The goal is to analyse the visual dimension of datasets by exploring the content that characterises the debate under consideration and expresses a certain degree of spatiality. In this case, spatiality is not only intended as a specific coordinate or location but envelops, in a broader sense, any element that may contain references or even abstractly represent places, spaces, people, events, and symbols that can be traced back to specific social spaces.

² The JRC is a European Commission research centre made up of scientific institutes that provide independent support in shaping the European Union's energy and environmental policies.

Figure 5. Imagesorter output which shows a visual media analysis to highlight some aspects of spatiality representations. (Source: Author's own elaboration).

The first aspect that catches the eye is the presence of a large yellow cluster with radioactive danger symbols. The symbol communicates alertness and may also convey a sense of proximity (temporal or spatial) to the source of the potential danger. Close and partially overlaid to the yellow cluster is possible to find an orange cluster which refers to NIMBY activism. In this case, the space narrated is the streets, the squares, and generally the places of protest. The Institutions cluster returns a picture of the institutional spaces in which the debate takes place, such as municipalities and council chambers representing both small towns and large cities. The Cartography cluster describes, with different regional or national maps, the spatiality of the potential sites and the relations of those places with other sites such as urban areas or national parks. The Natural Heritage cluster shows places such as monumental sites, UNESCO sites, or natural parks of undoubted landscape interest that could be affected by the presence of a waste Repository. Finally, the other main clusters Politics and Newspapers, do not primarily describe aspects of spatiality.

The qualitative content analysis served a double purpose: on the one hand, it helped to better put into context the dynamics observed with the social network analysis, and on the other, it revealed several hyper-partisan channels devoted to propaganda and others that conveyed misinformation and disinformation. Especially in the first weeks, there was misinformation about the number of repositories to be built and their precise location. Several channels and users erroneously shared reports claiming that repositories would be built in seven Italian regions, or even that as many as 67 separate repositories were planned. Some went so far as to provide entirely false details, such as the claim that “3 to 4 repositories” would be built in each region.

Figure 6. The image shows examples of content that disseminated misleading information regarding the National Radioactive Waste Repository. (Source: Author’s collage of Social Media content).

Some content used alarming tones and deliberately inaccurate words to raise the level of user outrage. There was rumours of "waste burial," terminology that, while technically correct (the waste will actually be placed below ground level), harkens back to imagery of illicit actions in waste management. The alt-news channels reported that the National Repository will house nuclear waste from northern Europe or "mysterious lands," an inaccuracy probably stemming from the news that some of the "Italian" radioactive waste currently stored in France and the UK will return to Italy to be placed in the National Repository. The issue was discussed in alarmist tones, with claims that it posed risks to groundwater and the wider ecosystem, and even accusations that the Italian State “wanted to kill everyone.” Much of these inferences came from

a Facebook group revolving around the populist and Eurosceptic political party Italexit, which in the last parliamentary elections garnered approximately 500,000 preferences but failed to win any seats. The pages of other political parties also participated in the misinformation and created confusion by addressing the National Repository as a "nuclear fuel Repository", as in the case of *LegaNord* party through its official page for the Chamber of Deputies.

Qualitative content analysis further highlighted the persistent North-South divide in Italy. Users from southern regions often described their territories as already burdened by other socio-environmental problems, stating that the South should not serve as a "national dumping ground." Two historical episodes have often been cited: the "Land of Fires" (Terra dei Fuochi) crisis in Campania, associated with toxic waste dumping and illegal burning (Peluso, 2015), and the Scanzano Jonico protests in 2003, when local mobilisation forced the Berlusconi government to withdraw its unilateral plan for a nuclear waste repository (Zinn, 2017).

These narratives are present in the collective memory and are brought to mind through YouTube videos, documentaries, and news archives shared online. Such references transcend spatio-temporal boundaries, evoking distant events in space and/or time (from Chernobyl and Fukushima to Hiroshima) to frame current struggles.

Discussion

Actors and network spatiality helped to shape the dynamics of the debate and, together with qualitative content analysis, revealed how multiple sub-issues and positions intertwined, providing multifaceted insight into the social complexity of the controversy. The analysis highlights the heterogeneous communication landscape typical of wicked problems where multiple perspectives collide.

The SNA shows that the debate over the National Radioactive Waste Repository involved a broad range of actors: activists and associations (LiberiOltre, Legambiente, Rete Nazionale Antinucleare, Change.org); companies and public agencies (SoginChannel, ISPRA); mainstream national news outlets (La Repubblica, Corriere della Sera, Il Sole 24 Ore, Huffington Post); local media (TG Antudo, TRM Network); alternative channels (CasaDelSoleTV); politicians at national and regional levels (Nello Musumeci, Rosa D'Amato, Eugenio Zoffili); municipalities (Torino, Carmagnola, Altamura, Melpignano, Paulilatino); and local mayors (Paolo Truzzu, Michele Emiliano, Gianluca Colletti), as well as ordinary users.

The debate typically originates in public Facebook groups, pages, or Twitter threads characterised by the recurring use of toponyms and region-specific hashtags. These digital environments can be described as "glocal" spaces (Roudometof, 2023): rooted in local contexts but capable of creating long-distance, cross-regional connections. Such glocal communication

reflects one of the central features of wicked environmental problems: their ability to mobilise local publics while simultaneously scaling up into national and even transnational discussions.

Most of these digital arenas are hyper-partisan, often serving as vehicles for propaganda and occasionally producing misinformation or disinformation. Nevertheless, these spaces also represent territorial arenas of resilience, where local identities are articulated, defended, and negotiated through communicative practices.

Pro-Repository positions originate primarily from activists such as AvvocatoAtomico and LiberiOltre and from Sogin, the company in charge of the project. Their arguments emphasise the need to align Italy with other European countries (ensuring the safe storage of low-, medium-, and high-level radioactive waste) and frame the National Repository as an opportunity for technological advancement and regulatory compliance.

Neutral or deliberative positions, typical of information channels such as Geopop and few political representatives (Manfredi Potenti and Jessica Costanzo among others), call for transparency and participation of all stakeholders (national authorities, territorial institutions, and citizens) in the decision-making process.

However, the predominant discourse remains oppositional. This is consistent with the literature on territorial resistance and the NIMBY (“Not In My Back Yard”) phenomenon (Bortoletti, 2004; Mura & Strazzer, 2013). Opposition to the Repository mainly originates from local news outlets, alternative media, and regional or municipal politicians. The spatial configuration that emerged from network mapping suggests a distinctive regional dimension of protest, leading to the concept of NIMYR (“Not In My Region”). NIMYR captures the alignment between NIMBY complaints from users and politicians' NIMTOO (Not in My Terms of Office) positions, combining geographical belonging and institutional identity. This alignment produces an interplay of regional pride, administrative autonomy and environmental justice that manifest both territorial segmentation and territorial resilience.

These concerns are reflected in the digital debate analysed here, from which two main strands of narrative have emerged:

- Health-related fears focus on risks of potential contamination of water and air, and risks related to waste transport.
- Wealth-related fears address potential damage to local economies, particularly in regions hosting products with Protected Designation of Origin (PDO) or Protected Geographical Indication (PGI) status, or UNESCO World Heritage sites.

Such concerns highlight the wicked nature of the problem: the overlap between long-term national planning and local perceptions of immediate risk and vulnerability.

These narratives reveal forms of territorial resilience: by expressing fears, people simultaneously reaffirm the value of their local environment and economy. This defensive attachment constitutes a communicative practice of care and protection, a resilient response through which local actors reassert control over their future within the JGT. Even when motivated by self-interest, these responses reveal adaptive capacities and the ability to mobilise collective identity around place.

Reflecting on the spatial relationship between the distribution of suitable areas and the geography of digital debates, some potentially interesting points emerged. The CNAPI sites located along the Puglia–Basilicata border appeared to encourage a coordinated regional stance, and this expectation was borne out empirically: actors in the two regions articulated largely convergent positions and mobilised in a broadly synergistic manner (as highlighted by posts containing messages referring collectively to “Puglia and Basilicata”). This pattern is also visible in the distribution of place references in the qualitative sample (N = 420): the joint territorial label “Puglia–Basilicata” occurs 54 times (12.9%), compared to 9 references to Puglia alone (2.1%) and 29 to Basilicata alone (6.9%), suggesting that the border configuration facilitated a shared territorial framing rather than two fully separate regional discourses.

Table 2. Regional distribution of Location emerged from qualitative analysis.

Region/category	Count	%
Non specificato (undefined)	165	39.3%
Puglia (Apulia)–Basilicata (joint label)	54	12.9%
Sicilia (Sicily)	52	12.4%
Sardegna (Sardinia)	48	11.4%
Basilicata	29	6.9%
Lazio	25	6.0%
Piemonte (Piedmont)	22	5.2%
Toscana (Tuscany)	13	3.1%
Puglia (Apulia)	9	2.1%
Lombardia (Lombardy)	2	0.5%
Campania	1	0.2%

By contrast, the high concentration of temporary storage facilities in Piedmont suggests a greater degree of institutional and societal familiarity with nuclear-related infrastructures. Consistent with this interpretation, Piedmont is comparatively less salient in the place-referenced material (22 items, 5.2%) than several territorial focal points in the debate such as Sicilia (52, 12.4%) and Sardegna (48, 11.4%), and it also remains less salient than the border framing “Puglia–Basilicata” (54, 12.9%). While these descriptive patterns cannot establish

causality, they are compatible with the view that prior exposure and institutional embedding may contribute to a less heated or at least less place-centred controversy than in regions where the repository is more readily framed as an unfamiliar and externally imposed risk.

Overall, the regional geography of the debate largely mirrors the spatial distribution of candidate areas identified in the CNAPI, insofar as place references concentrate in regions that recur as territorial focal points in public contestation (notably Sicilia and Sardegna). At the same time, it is possible to observe instances of partial discursive de-territorialisation. First, a substantial share of items refers to Italy in general without specifying a subnational location (25.5% of items), indicating that the controversy frequently circulates in non-localised terms. Second, although Campania is rarely referenced explicitly, it enters the debate through symbolic place narratives (e.g., “Terra dei Fuochi”), through which radioactive waste is integrated into a broader Italian North–South cleavage frame. Taken together, these patterns point to a debate that is simultaneously anchored to CNAPI-relevant territorial focal points and capable of being re-routed through wider symbolic geographies in which risk, neglect, and environmental injustice are articulated beyond the immediate geography of candidate sites.

For public projects of this magnitude, especially those involving sensitive issues such as radioactive waste, effective communication is essential. Well-structured communication must include a reliable network of experts and collaborators, facilitate the validation of online information, provide access to data visualisations with different levels of granularity, and increase the explainability of content flagged as disinformation (Kyza et al., 2020). This approach should help prevent the topic from suddenly becoming the subject of heated debate, reducing the risks of escalating social conflicts and misinformation.

The Potential Impact on Planning Process

While data does not allow causal attribution between online discourse and policy outcomes, it remains possible to identify governance-relevant pathways through which digital contestation may shape institutional dynamics: by elevating salience and media attention, by intensifying legitimacy disputes around procedures and expertise, or by structuring conflicts between local/regional publics and national objectives.

The qualitative analysis highlighted problematic information dynamics: partisan channels focused on propaganda, emotional appeals, and oppositional mobilisation rhetoric often overshadow balanced conversation. The radioactive waste controversy erupted suddenly into public discourse, producing chaotic and emotionally driven debate based more on perception than evidence. This pattern aligns with the complex structure of the problem: information uncertainty and emotional overload reinforce mistrust, making consensus elusive. Without

effective communication strategies (Goldstein et al., 2020), oppositional mobilisation can escalate into social conflict and institutional paralysis.

The analysis uncovered that many political actors (regional governments, councils, municipalities, and mayors) adopted NIMTOO (“Not In My Term of Office”) attitudes (Tipaldo, 2015), using the controversy as a political instrument to criticise national administrations or gain consensus. This dynamic is often vertical: lower-tier institutions (regional and municipal) attacking upper tiers (national government). In this context, local journalism and institutions play a fundamental role, as they have a duty to communicate transparently with the public and act as intermediaries, avoiding fuelling conflict, especially in areas that are potential hotspots for protest.

Beyond discursive contestation, the qualitative analysis also points to institutional mobilisation at the local level. An example could be municipalities activating formal and informal participatory channels such as council sessions and signature campaigns to articulate opposition and to position themselves within the ever-changing context of the dispute. These actions were not limited to municipalities directly implicated by candidate areas; rather, mobilisation also emerged in proximate or symbolically connected localities, suggesting that perceived risk and legitimacy claims travelled through relational territorial logics rather than remaining confined to administrative boundaries. Illustrative cases include the convening of municipal council meetings in Arborea (25 January) and Melpignano (20 February), a signature-collection campaign in Carmagnola (9 January), and the convening of a municipal council session accompanied by a formal motion reaffirming opposition to nuclear waste in Paulilatino (18 January). These episodes represent a measurable institutional response in the form of agenda-setting and formal position-taking, even where they do not directly alter siting decisions.

A particularly salient example is the 2023 case of Trino Vercellese (Province of Vercelli), the only municipality to formally self-nominate as host of the National Repository. That proposal, however, was considered incompatible with the siting criteria because the area lies too close to the Po River. The mayor’s willingness to nominate Trino was linked to the town’s long-standing involvement with nuclear waste management: since the 1960s, radioactive materials have been stored in facilities connected to the former Enrico Fermi nuclear power plant, which is still undergoing decommissioning. The initiative prompted opposition first from environmental groups and later from institutional actors, including neighbouring municipalities and the Provinces of Alessandria and Vercelli. The mayor subsequently withdrew the self-nomination roughly four months after it had been approved (Carboni, 2024). Digital communication accelerates the circulation of information and lowers the time lag between institutional decisions and public reaction. In cases such as Trino Vercellese, a municipal decision can

rapidly become shared knowledge across multiple online arenas, triggering immediate interpretation, contestation, and re-framing by heterogeneous actors. This speed can generate positive effects such as wider transparency and faster mobilisation of affected publics, but it can also amplify negative dynamics, including misinterpretation, strategic framing, and escalating distrust, particularly when the issue is already marked by uncertainty and contested expertise.

The study findings could be interpreted as evidence about the conditions of public legitimacy and contestation that institutions must navigate, rather than as direct evidence of policy change, who is nevertheless affected by more complex reasons that go beyond the online debate. During a press conference in May 2025, Environment Minister Gilberto Pichetto Fratin stated that the government was moving away from the plan to build a single, centralised national repository. He presented a primarily logistical argument, suggesting that a sole facility would imply frequent long-distance transport of radioactive waste across the country. As an alternative, he pointed to a more distributed approach, either developing three sites (North, Center and South) or relying more heavily on the network of existing temporary storage facilities, thereby signalling a departure from a technical and political pathway that has been under discussion for more than twenty years (ilPost, 2025). However, the dispute remains unresolved, and subsequent reporting suggests that the government has continued to consider alternative configurations, including the possibility of reverting to a single facility depending on territorial willingness and institutional decisions, rather than definitively abandoning the centralised option (Corriere della Sera, 2025).

Digital platforms and social media in particular, provide access to digitally visible publics and can support planning by revealing how controversies are framed, amplified, and connected to territorial identities and legitimacy claims. It is important to emphasise that such data should not be considered as a proxy for population opinion; however, single-platform research suggests that platform debate can still be analytically informative. Studies have shown that even when users are demographically and politically skewed, the distribution of arguments may mirror key patterns observed in survey data, indicating that social media can capture meaningful contours of public reasoning rather than only noise (van Klingeren et al., 2021). For planners, this implies that digital contestation is best approached as a structural feature of hybrid governance: it can be a risk when visibility is shaped by highly mobilised minorities, antagonistic framing, or rapid attention cycles; but also a resource insofar as it surfaces emerging concerns, identifies trusted intermediaries and highlights geographically specific “hotspots” that may not be fully visible through formal consultation channels. Building on these insights, the research extends beyond single-platform inference by adopting a multi-platform design (Twitter and Facebook) to assess

which patterns are robust across different affordances and publics, and what this implies for scale-sensitive stakeholder engagement in contested siting processes.

Conclusions

This social media research has shed light on the Italian debate surrounding the Italian National Radioactive Waste Repository, illustrating how environmental controversies unfold in digital communication spaces. This study adopts a digital methods perspective that examines digitally visible publics rather than the full population affected by the siting process. Accordingly, the analysis is subject to well-known constraints of spatial work with platform data, including linguistic ambiguity and uneven geolocation signals, as well as representativeness limits shaped by platform cultures and territorial inequalities in access and participation. These dynamics may underrepresent groups that are less present on the analysed platforms (e.g., older residents or digitally marginalised communities). To reduce dependence on any single platform's affordances, the study draws on two distinct platforms with different user bases and interaction logics and attend specifically to local media and regional actors that often mediate between online debate and offline publics. The findings therefore map how the controversy is networked, spatialised, and framed within hybrid digital environments, offering insight into the visibility and legitimacy dynamics of contested siting rather than a measure of population-level attitudes.

Methodologically, the study demonstrates the potential of a quanti-qualitative approach that integrates NLP and SNA with qualitative content and visual analysis. This combination allowed for the spatialisation of discourse and actors, producing a detailed mapping of the digital ecosystem around the radioactive waste debate. The use of Issue Spatiality (Stoltenberg, 2021) provided a framework for interpreting how territorial identities and environmental concerns are constructed online, while the integration of network analysis revealed the relational structure at the core of this conflict.

Findings reveal territorial segmentation and oppositional mobilization in the digital public sphere, dominated by local media, activist networks, and regional voices. The pattern of opposition to the National Repository, summarised in the acronym NIMYR emerged as a strong spatial and emotional marker, expressing collective fears and regional identities that represent a response to a perceived territorial injustice.

Within the broader framework of the JGT, this case exemplifies a wicked problem involving overlapping conflicts and governance territorial segmentation. The Italian case illustrates how local actors use digital platforms to contest policies that they perceive as being imposed from above. In this light, social media function not only as amplifiers of oppositional mobilisation but

also as arenas where communities experiment with adaptive responses, constructing narratives of resistance and care that sustain socio-spatial cohesion.

At the same time, the research underscores the importance of political communication and transparency in managing controversial projects. Public acceptance of environmentally sensitive infrastructures depends not only on the perception of benefits but on the reduction of perceived risk and the establishment of trust (Seidl et al., 2013). Without effective communication strategies, oppositional mobilisation deepens, leading to decision-making stalemates, an outcome visible in the persistent opposition to the National Repository.

In conclusion, the study highlights that radioactive waste management cannot be addressed with purely technical or top-down approaches. It requires sensitivity to the complex nature of environmental controversies and the ability to communicate local practices.

By revealing how digital arenas mediate between local concerns and broader policy frameworks, this research contributes to understanding how emerging contestation and public discourse become a critical dimension of environmental transition governance.

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Conflict of interest

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Author statement on the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools

I confirm that AI tools (ChatGPT, Grammarly, DeepL) were used only in a supportive capacity in the preparation of this manuscript (e.g. language editing, formatting, or idea organisation). All substantive arguments, interpretations, and conclusions are the sole work of the author, and the author take full responsibility for the content. I also confirm that all references cited are real, have been verified by the author, and are not AI-generated or fabricated.

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